

ASSESSMENT OF YIELD LOSSES DUE TO MAJOR INSECT PEST IN CASHEW

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Abstract:

Cashew is an important commercial crop grown in dry and barren lands contributing considerably to foreign exchange of India. The national average annual production is 7.42 tons with an average productivity of 707 kg/ha and India enjoys a third position in production. The actual production of the crop is not realized due to the infestation by insect pests during the crop phase. Around 50 insect pests were reported from India) of which, only a few were considered as major pests. Tea mosquito bug, *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret (Hemiptera: Miridae) is an economically important insect pest, which alone causes 30-50 per cent yield loss. The average fruit yield on the basis of seven year research was estimated up to 425.85 kg in unprotected plot as compare to higher up to 568.42 kg in protected plot. The avoidable crop loss of 25.08 per cent was assessed in unprotected plot, which substantiated to the economic loss of Rs. 12831/ha. With yield loss of 142.57 kg/ha.

Key word: Yield loss assessment, Cashew, Tea Mosquito bug, Thrips

Introduction

Cashew is an important commercial crop grown in dry and barren lands contributing considerably to foreign exchange of India. The national average annual production is 7.42 tons with an average productivity of 707 kg/ha (DCCD, 2019) and India enjoys a third position in production. The actual production of the crop is not realized due to the infestation by insect pests during the crop phase. Around 50 insect pests were reported from India (Devasahayam and Nair, 1986) of which, only a few were considered as major pests. Tea mosquito bug, *Helopeltis antonii* Signoret (Hemiptera: Miridae) is an economically important insect pest, which alone causes 30-50 per cent yield loss (Abraham and Nair 1981; Sundararaju and Sundarababu 1999b) and even complete yield loss in outbreak situation (Devasahayam and Nair 1986). Cashew stem and root borer is other important pest threatening the crop stand. Leaf miner, *Acrocercops syngamma* Meyrick, apple and nut borer, *Thylacoptila paurosema* Meyrick and flower thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood were also reported to occur regularly but of minor importance. However, very often control failures have been reported in outbreak situations with 30 per cent yield loss even in sprayed plots (Sundararaju and Sundarababu 1999). The tea mosquito bug alone has a potential to cause 40 to 50 percent yield losses in cashew and in severer outbreak the pest causes yield losses up to 100 percent (Anonymous, 1998). TMB causes serious damage to the tender leaf, growing tip, inflorescence, apple and the nut. Looking into the economic importance of tea mosquito bug, the present investigation aimed Assessment of yield losses due to major insect pest in cashew.

Material And Methods

Field experiment was conducted during 2015-16 and 2021-22 at Agriculture Experimental Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Paria (20°26'39" N, 72°55'58" E, 15 mmsl) to Vengurla-4 varieties of cashew for their yield loss assessment due to tea mosquito bug and thrips. The varieties Vengurla-4 were evaluated based on damage score.

Treatments: Two

1. Protected
2. Control (Unprotected)

Insect-pest

1st spray of Lambda cyhalothrin 5 EC @ 0.003 % (6ml / 10lit. water) at flushing + 2nd spray of Acetamiprid 20 SP @ 0.004% (2g / 10 lit. water) at flowering and 3rd spray of Clothianidin 50 % WDG (6 ml / 10 lit. water) at fruit setting, if needed.

Tea mosquito bug:

Adults and nymph present in marked or 52 leader shoots in any Side of canopy were counted. Total number of shoots (Non-flowering lateral) and panicles (flowering laterals) were recorded separately in above area. The damaged shoots/ panicles were also to be recoded using 0-4 scale.

0=No damage

1=1 to 3 necrotic streaks/lesions on the shoot/panicle including apple and nut

2= 4 to 6 coalescing or non-coalescing lesions/streaks on the shoot/panicle including apple and nut

3=Above six coalescing or non-coalescing lesions/streaks on the shoot/panicle including apple and nut

4=Lesion/streaks on fluent or wilting or drying of affected shoot /panicle including apple and nut

Total score

Mean Score value= _____

Total number of lateral shoots + panicles

Inflorescence thrips:

Damage (corky growth or presence of scab) on 100 nuts and apples/tree selected at random needs to be scored as below

0=No damage

1=1-25 percent nut or apple surface damage (upto¼ of the damage surface area)

2= 26-50 percent nut or apple surface damage (up to 1/2 of the damage surface area)

3= 51-75 percent nut or apple surface damage (up to ¾ of the damage surface area)

4=76-100 percent nut or apple surface damage (more than ¾ of the damage surface area)

The damage grade cause by TMB and Thrips were recorded from leader shoot at flushing, flowering and fruit setting time. The percent damage cause by leaf and blossom webber, shoot tip caterpillar, leaf minor and apple and nut borer were counted at the time of leader shoot at flushing, flowering and fruit setting time. A total ten trees will be recorded at the time of flushing, flowering and fruit setting. The damage score was record on scale base (0-4 scale). Observations were recorded 3 DAS, 7 DAS and 14 days after spray, **plant protection measure to be adopted as on Appearance pest.** Incidence of leaf and blossom webber and Apple and nut borer was recorded prior to a day of each spray and again at 30 days after spray.

Mean number of nuts Mean number of nuts

Yield loss% = $\frac{\text{in protected panicles-in unprotected panicles}}{\text{Mean number of nuts in protected panicles}} \times 100$

Two trees in each variety were selected for observations. Scoring for tea mosquito bug infestation was done during the regular flushing and flowering season. *i.e.*, October to March. On each tree, an area of 0.5 m × 0.5 m quadrant was marked on four side's *viz.*, East, West, North and South. Observations were recorded on total number of shoots and panicles in each quadrant and the damage score of tea mosquito bug affected shoot and panicle. The mean score per tree was worked out from the total score values of four quadrants divided by the total number of shoots and panicles. The mean score values recorded at fortnightly intervals on shoots and panicles from two sample trees per variety was assessed separately for each year. Three observations were recorded for the shoots and panicles separately during each year. The pooled mean of eight years data were used for comparison.

Results and Discussion

The average fruit yield on the basis pooled data of seven year research was estimated up to 425.85 kg in unprotected plot as compare to higher up to 568.42 kg in protected plot. The avoidable crop loss of 25.08 per cent was assessed in unprotected plot, which substantiated to the economic loss of Rs. 12831/ha. With yield loss of 142.57 kg/ha. (Table: 1). The infestation of Tea mosquito bug (TMB) was found in unprotected and protected plot were compared on the basis of pest (TMB damage scale) infestation. The damage scale of pest of cashew to the tune of 1.70 damage score (0-4) in unprotected plot as compared to 0.79 damage score (0-4) in protected plot. (Table: 2). The infestation of Thrips was found in unprotected and protected plot were compared on the basis of pest (Thrips damage scale) infestation. The damage scale of pest of cashew to the tune of 1.15 damage score (0-4)

in unprotected plot as compared to 0.57 damage score (0-4) in protected plot.(Table:3). Above report are supports to the present findings. The unsprayed cashew trees with no ant recorded maximum damage of 47.42 + 3.71 and 52.36 + 3.86% in coastal and maidan tracts, respectively. Higher nut yield of 3.70 kg/tree in coastal and 2.43 kg /tree in maidan tract was recorded from the trees fully colonized with *O.smaragdina*. The sequential sprays of monocrotophos (0.05%) - β -cyhalothrin (0.005%) - carbaryl (0.10%) registered the least per cent TMB damage, higher nut yield and high C:B ratio. (Manjanaik & Chakravarthy., 2013)

Conclusion:

The Seven year pooled data indicated that the average yield loss due to cashew pest infestation was exhibited up to 25.08 per cent which substantiated to the economics loss of Rs. 12831/ha.

Table 1: Assessment of loss due to insect pests in cashew (Pooled of seven years)

Treatments	Fruit yield (kg/ha)								% avoidable loss	Net economic loss(Rs./ha)
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-2020	2020-21	2021-22	Average Yield		
Untreated plot	440	449	418	406	414	424	430	425.85	25.08	12831/- **
Treated plot	612	624	545	536	542	556	564	568.42		

**Average Raw Cashew nuts sale price:Rs.90.00/Kg

Table 2: Assessment of loss due to insect pests in cashew (Pooled of seven years)

Treatments	TMB damage score (0-4)							Average score of TMB
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-2020	2020-21	2021-22	
Untreated plot	1.88	1.86	1.80	1.60	1.56	1.62	1.58	1.70
Treated plot	0.93	0.88	0.84	0.72	0.76	0.72	0.68	0.79
Two sample "t" test significance	2.26 *	2.26*	2.22*	2.16*	2.14*	2.08*	2.02*	2.16*

*Sample are significantly different at 5 % level of significance

Table 3: Assessment of loss due to insect pests in cashew (Pooled of seven years)

Treatments	Thrips damage score(0-4)							Average score of Thrips
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-2020	2020-21	2021-22	
Untreated plot	1.33	1.28	1.22	1.12	1.08	1.02	1.00	1.15
Treated plot	0.75	0.69	0.64	0.52	0.56	0.46	0.42	0.57
Two sample "t" test significance	2.10	2.10	2.06	1.94	1.88	1.82	1.78	1.95

*Sample are significantly different at 5 % level of significance

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